

Synergetic Effects of Thin Ply and Nanostitching Studied by Synchrotron Radiation Computed Tomography

Estelle Kalfon-Cohen¹, Reed Kopp¹, Carolina Furtado^{1,3,4}, Xinchen Ni², Nathan Fritz², Albertino Arteiro^{3,4}, Gregor Borstnar⁵, Mark N. Mavrogordato⁵, S. Mark Spearing⁵, Pedro P. Camanho^{3,4}, and Brian L. Wardle¹

¹ Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Massachusetts Institute of Technology,
77 Massachusetts Avenue, Cambridge, MA 02139 USA

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology,
77 Massachusetts Avenue, Cambridge, MA 02139 USA

³ DEMec, Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto,
Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, s/n, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal

⁴ INEGI, Instituto de Ciência e Inovação em Engenharia Mecânica e Engenharia Industrial,
Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 400, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal

⁵ Faculty of Engineering and the Environment, University of Southampton,
Highfield, Southampton, SO17 1BJ, UK

Keywords: Carbon fiber reinforced composite, Thin ply, Carbon nanotubes,
Synchrotron radiation computed tomography

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic composite thin ply laminates are reinforced in interlaminar regions with vertically-aligned carbon nanotubes (A-CNTs) using a technique known as “nanostitching.” In this study, we report the successful interlaminar nanostitching of thin ply laminates and the reinforcing effects associated with the addition of A-CNTs. Testing under short beam shear loading configuration yields a 17% improvement in the interlaminar shear strength of thin ply laminates as compared to the equivalent thick laminate and an additional 3% improvement after nanostitching. *In situ* double edge notched tensile testing, which generally demonstrates a reduced damage state for thin ply vs. conventional thickness plies, exhibits minimal damage accumulation and progression with increasing tensile load as visualized using synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT). Although the effect of nanostitching was not clearly distinguished in the *in situ* tensile tests, these results are an initial outlook via *in situ* microtomographic volume imaging on the synergetic effects of nanostitching and thin ply morphologies on the failure progression of aerospace-grade unidirectional laminated composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites are routinely used today in primary aerostructures, in part thanks to the maturation of the technology and parts manufacturing using pre-impregnated composite fibers (prepregs). Consisting of a stack of individual layers, a prepreg laminate has limited out-of-plane mechanical properties caused by weak interlaminar bonding, inducing susceptibility to early delamination. An emerging technology is a thin ply version of conventional prepregs. Thin plies are manufactured by spreading down the fiber tow before resin pre-impregnation, leading to improved mechanical properties at the lamina and laminate level [1]. For instance, at the lamina level, composite parts made with thin ply laminates show delayed delamination and higher load bearing capacity under compression, whereas at the laminate level, they appear to delay delamination and other forms of damage in tensile loading [2, 3]. This advantage is inherent to the morphology of the thin ply, especially its thickness which is inversely related to the resistance of a crack to propagation. Drawbacks associated with thin ply are few but have to be addressed. For instance, the number of laminae required to manufacture a standard thickness part is now increased. Considering a thin ply with one-third of the thickness of a conventional prepreg, the number of interfaces is now tripled, increasing the risk of early

delamination.

In this study, we report the use of aligned nanoscale fibers (carbon nanotubes, CNTs) to reinforce interfaces of a thin ply laminate through an architecture termed “nanostitching.” Nanostitching leads to a hybrid architecture, where aligned CNTs are integrated into the interface of fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) plies, such as carbon fiber and glass fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs and GFRPs) [4-5]. Previous studies have reported increases in both the in-plane properties and interlaminar fracture toughness of thin ply composites compared to conventional composites [5,6-8], but understanding of the dynamic 3D reinforcement mechanism is still insufficient.

Typically, composite materials researchers explore the quality of laminae interfaces and reinforcement mechanisms via optical and electron microscopy of polished cross sections of laminate coupons. However, these are only 2D visualizations and no versatile technique exists to date to assess the internal quality of the laminate, beyond micro-computed tomography. Particularly, as a nondestructive volumetric imaging technique, synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT) provides unparalleled insight for identification of mechanisms associated with CNT reinforcement by enabling visualization via x-ray scanning of both *ex situ* and real-time *in situ* damage initiation and propagation. Seminal studies based on SRCT revealed unprecedented understanding of the failure mechanisms of laminate composites by correlating microtomographic imaging and mechanical testing [9-11]. Herein, employing SRCT to qualitatively corroborate mechanical behavior, it was hypothesized that similar or even greater results could be realized with advanced thin ply prepregs featuring nanostitching due to the increase in the number of interfaces for thin vs. standard thickness plies.

In the following sections, we report the fabrication, characterization, and mechanical testing of nanostitched thin ply laminates. Specifically, the use of SRCT to visualize damage and damage progression in nanostitched thin ply laminates gives us an insight into the synergetic effect of thin ply and nanostitch reinforcement.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and laminate fabrication

20 μm height aligned carbon nanotube forests were grown on 3 cm x 4 cm silicon wafer substrates according to a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process [5]. The final stage of the process includes a water-assisted delamination step allowing forests to be easily removed from silicon wafers.

A quasi-isotropic (QI) $([0/90/\pm 45]_6)_s$ thin ply laminate was manufactured using Toho Tenax HTS40/Q-1112 unidirectional prepreg; CNT nanostitches were included in 15 of the midplane interfaces between the plies using the process previously described (Method I) [6]. HTS40/Q-1112 is an aerospace-grade epoxy and carbon fiber prepreg with a ply thickness of 54 μm . The panel was subsequently cured in an autoclave according to the manufacturer specifications 2 hours at 120°C and 7 bar pressure. The comparison to standard thickness ply laminates was done using a QI $([0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3]_2)_s$ baseline version of the thin ply panel (named here “Thick”) and designed by laying up consecutively 3 thin plies to reach the equivalent standard thickness of 150 μm . A schematic of the layup sequences are displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Thin and thick ply layups from Toho Tenax Q-1112

For both layups, a baseline panel (not nanostitched) was manufactured and tested. The thickness of the laminates was measured and reported for each configuration: 2.98 mm and 2.92 mm for thick and thin types, respectively, and 2.99 mm and 2.96 mm for nanostitched thick and thin, respectively (± 0.025 mm). For each configuration, at least 8 coupons of dimensions of 5.9 mm x 17.5 mm were cut and polished.

2.2 Morphological characterization of the interlaminar region thickness

Optical and scanning electron microscopy images were used to assess the transfer quality of the nanostitching and rough damage assessment of *post mortem* samples. Assuring a fully-filled interface along the specimen and controlled morphology at the micron scale is thought to be key to maximize the strengthening and toughening effects. Here, the transfer quality of the nanostitching is assessed through optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM); optical methods allow high-level observation of overall laminate morphology, whereas SEM allows sufficient resolution to identify and characterize the CNT nanostitch morphology (thickness and continuity), as well as the interface with the adjacent plies. SEM micrographs of the specimen cross section reveal that CNT layers closely fill the gap at the interface between without increasing significantly the interlaminar thickness (and in turn, the overall lamina thickness) (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Scanning electron micrographs of (a) baseline and (b) nanostitched thin ply SBS coupons. The nanostitched regions are highlighted in green (b).

Insights into CNT filling ratio at the interface between plies are gained through SEM inspection of the interlaminar region. Figure 3 reports the thickness of the interlaminar region and of the CNT nanostitch versus baseline (reference) in thin and thick coupons, showing that nanostitching the interlayer region results in a slight increase of the overall laminate thickness (less than 2% for thin ply) and of the local interlaminar thickness of the thin-ply laminate (about 5% increase).

Figure 3: Interlaminar thickness measured through SEM inspections in thick and thin ply laminates.

2.3 *Ex situ* short beam shear mechanical testing

The effect of nanostitching was investigated through static short beam shear (SBS) testing, a type of 3-point bending loading technique. SBS testing configuration requires minimum machining of the specimen and was used here as preliminary testing before moving to more targeted substructural testing. Polished samples were tested according to ASTM D2344 [12] on a Zwick/Roell Z010 instrument at the Institute of Nanotechnology at MIT, using a 10 kN load cell and displacement controlled-loading at a rate of 1 mm/min until occurrence of failure, which is defined by greater than 30% force drop or midspan displacement greater than the specimen thickness. At least 7 specimens were tested for statistical purposes.

Thick and thin ply coupons previously tested under SBS configuration were scanned *ex situ* using a 20 keV x-ray energy beam with projections captured at a $\sim 0.7\mu\text{m}$ voxel resolution and 50 ms exposure. SRCT experiments were carried out at the ID 19 beamline at the European Synchrotron Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble, France.

2.4 *In situ* double edge notched tensile mechanical testing

Double edge notched specimens were machined with two 1:1 mm radius edge notches (see Figure 4 (right)) using a high precision waterjet (Omax); aluminum tabs were bonded to both ends of the specimen to facilitate load application. The specimens were subjected to uniaxial tension with stresses ranging from 30% to 100% of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and SRCT scans were carried out at each load step. For the *in situ* experiment, the samples were loaded using the Deben tensile test apparatus described in Figure 4 (left).

Figure 4: SRCT *in situ* loading experiments: (left) schematic of the Deben *in situ* loading stage used at the ESRF (Reproduced from [9]) and (right) double edge notched specimen. The specimen comprises aluminum tabs to minimize grip compliance.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 *Ex situ* short beam shear results

Testing under the SBS configuration, typical loading curves (see Figure 5a) for both thick and thin systems drop at slightly higher loads when the laminate is nanostitched. Using the maximum load to compute interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), the increase of maximum force is translated into a 3% increase of the ILSS for both systems (see Figure 5b). The effect of the thin ply morphology is especially pronounced when the ILSS of nanostitched thin ply system is compared to the baseline thick system, exhibiting a 17% increase. The statistically significant increase of the ILSS demonstrates that the major part of the improvement is due to the thin ply nature of the prepreg rather than the nanostitching. However, it should be noted that the rather low 3% improvement over reference samples is in line with the 8% improvement noted for IM7/8552 systems [6] and underlies the identical mechanisms involving CNT nanostitching across different prepreg morphologies.

Figure 5: Thin ply and nanostitch synergies: (a) representative SBS load-displacement curves and (b) interlaminar shear strength for thin and thick ply specimens with standard error.

Optical images of post failure cross sections in Figure 6 reveal cracks and delaminations involved in the SBS failure process. While the equivalent thick ply system shows intralaminar cracks, these are completely suppressed in the thin ply system, with no relation to nanostitching. In addition, when the thin ply is nanostitched, the location of the delamination across the thickness of the thin ply is often shifted from the center of the laminate (as observed in baseline) to the side. This behavior was observed only in the thin ply system and is apparently due to the few CNT layers added in the thick version (5 nanostitches in thin ply vs. 15 in thick ply). The same profiles were observed for AS4/8552 system in similar experiments.

Figure 6: Optical micrographs of SBS coupons after testing, showing the location of cracks and delaminations: (a) thick, (b) thick nanostitched (c) thin , and (d) thin nanostitched. The dashed box highlights the nanostitched area.

SEM inspection of the damaged area (see Figure 7) shows partial delamination through nanostitched interface, exposing free standing CNTs in the broken section. This observation suggests that the CNT pullout mechanism was actively involved in increasing tolerance to delamination.

Figure 7: Scanning electron micrographs of typical delamination damage in a nanostitched thin ply coupon after failing under the SBS test configuration. In the inset, a close up of CNT pull-out.

3.2 *In situ* double edge notched tensile results

In situ SRCT experiments provide insight into the mechanisms involved in delayed failure often exhibited by thin ply. Double-notched coupons of thin and nanostitched thin ply were machined and tested under tension, as this configuration simulates a typical design case. Although no significant improvement was measured for the notched UTS of the nanostitched thin ply (see Figure 8), *in situ* SRCT scans exhibit damage progression in thin ply specimens as tensile loading is increased from 70% to 95% of the UTS (see Figure 9). As negligible damage formed near the center of the notch for all loadings, the SRCT images are extracted from location along the notch at ~ 0.7 mm below the notch center, where visible damage was most commonly found. This particular location was selected for each 95% UTS load step and tracked spatially as the load step was decreased to 70% UTS by tracking common geometrical features at the specimen edges. Damage segmentation of the SRCT images was performed using the ImageJ software package. In each case, damage initiates at the jagged notch edge and propagates inward towards the specimen center. Although nanostitching has no noticeable effect on the damage state associated with this loading configuration, the use of *in situ* SRCT confirms the formation of minimum apparent damage in thin ply laminates during loading and the delay of subcritical damage at loads close to maximum UTS.

Figure 8: Double edge notched ultimate tensile strength in baseline and CNT nanostitched laminate coupons. The error bars specify standard error.

Figure 9: *In situ* SRCT of thin ply double-notched coupons loaded in tension. Limited damage (highlighted in red) develops in thin ply specimens at a loading of 70% notched UTS, but propagates into larger intralaminar cracks as loading is increased to 95% UTS. The right side of each image corresponds to the notched edge, whereas the left side approaches the center of each specimen. The tensile loading direction was aligned with the 0° plies.

As a comparison, standard prepreg laminate coupons made of AS4/8552 were tested under the same *in situ* loading conditions and displayed multiple large transverse cracks and free edge delaminations [13]. The suppression of damage extent, particularly intralaminar cracks, at loadings close to the UTS confirm the superior mechanical performance of thin ply, while the delay of delamination in the nanostitched area seems to confirm the strengthening and toughening effects of the CNT interfacial nanostitches.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we report the nanostitching of 54 gsm thin ply laminates by aligned carbon nanotubes. We show that the interlaminar shear strength of thin ply laminates is improved by 17% over the equivalent thick ply. Furthermore, a significant 3% addition is measured after nanostitching the thin laminate. Observation of damaged regions in *post mortem* specimens reveals minimal damage and the absence of delamination in the nanostitched region, highlighting the toughening effect of the CNT via nanofiber pullout and crack bridging. We report the use of *in situ* synchrotron radiation micro-computed tomography to visualize damage progression in double edge notched configuration whilst loaded in tension. The sequential scans over a range of loading up to 95% ultimate tensile strength reveal a minimal effect of the nanostitching on damage progression, although slight improvement in the ultimate tensile strength is reported in the thin nanostitched configuration. Further work should compare the thin ply laminate to the equivalent thick ply laminate to highlight the positive effect of ply morphology on damage progression.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the U.S Office of Naval Research under grant/contract number N00014-13-1-0213, and by Airbus, Embraer, Lockheed Martin, Saab AB, Hexcel, Saertex, TohoTenax, and ANSYS through MIT's Nano-Engineered Composite aerospace Structures (NECST) Consortium. This work was partially funded by National Funds through FCT – Fundação para Ciência

e a Tecnologia in the scope of project MITP-TB/PFM/0005/2013. This work made use of facilities supported in part by the U. S. Army Research Laboratory and the U. S. Army Research Office through the Institute for Soldier Nanotechnologies, under contract number W911NF-13-D-0001, the facilities at the U.S. Army Natick Solidier R, D & E Center (NSRDEC), and carried out in part through the use of MIT's Microsystems Technology Laboratories. The SRCT experiments were performed on beamline ID 19 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), Grenoble, France. We are grateful to Lukas Helfen and Elodie Boller at the ESRF for providing assistance in using beamline ID 19. The first, second, fourth, fifth, ninth, and tenth authors would like to thank FCT for financial support. This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship Program under Grant No. 1122374. Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation. The authors thank the entire necslab at MIT and lab members at μ -VIS X-Ray Imaging Center at University of Southampton for valuable discussion and input.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kawabe K, Tomoda S, Matsuo T. A pneumatic process for spreading reinforcing fiber tow. In: The 42nd international SAMPE symposium & exhibition, Anaheim, CA; May 4–8, 1997.
- [2] Sihn, S., Kim, R.Y., Kawabe, K. and Tsai, SW., *Compos Sci. Technol.* 2007; 67:996-1008.
- [3] Arteiro, A, Catalanotti, G., Melro, A.R., Linde, P. and Camanho, P.P, *Composites Part A* 2015; 79-90.
- [4] Gorbatikh L., Wardle, BL. and Lomov, SV. *MRS Bulletin*, Volume41, no. 9, September 2016, pp. 672-677.
- [5] Garcia, E., Wardle, B., and Hart, A.J., *Composites: Part A.* 2008; 39:1065–1070.
- [6] Lewis, D and Wardle, B.L. “Interlaminar Shear Strength Investigation of Aligned Carbon Nanotube-Reinforced Prepreg Composite Interfaces,” *AIAA SciTech* 2015, Kissimmee, Florida 5-9 January 2015.
- [7] Kalfon-Cohen, Lingchuan L., Kladitis P., Shuter,E., Lewis, DJ., Orr-Ravine, J., and Wardle, BL. “Interlaminar Morphology and Strength of Woven Carbon Fiber Prepreg Laminates Reinforced with Aligned Carbon Nanotubes” *AIAA SciTech* 2016, San Diego, California 4-8 January 2016.
- [8] R. Guzmán de Villoria, P. Hallander, L. Ydrefors, P. Nordin and B. L. Wardle. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* (2016), 133:33–39.
- [9] Wright, P., Moffat, A., Sinclair, I. and Spearing, S.M. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 2010; 70(10):1444-1452.
- [10] Swolfs, Y., Morton, H., Scott, A.E., Gorbatikh, L., Reed, P.A.S, Sinclair, I., Spearing, S.M. and Verpoest, I., *Composites Part A.* 2015; 77:106-113
- [11] Scott, A.E., Mavrogordato, M., Wright, P., Sinclair, I. and Spearing, S.M., *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 2011;71:1471-1477.
- [12] ASTM D2344 “Standard Test Method for Short-Beam Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials and Their Laminates”
- [13] Ni, X., Kalfon-Cohen, E., Furtado, C., Arteiro, A., Valdes, G., Hank, T., Fritz, N., Kopp, R., Borstnar, G. Mavrogordato, M.N., Spearing, S.M., Camanho, P.P. and Wardle, B.L. “Interlaminar Reinforcement of Carbon Fiber Composites Using Aligned Carbon Nanotubes,” submitted to 21st International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM), Xi'an, China, Aug. 20-25, 2017